

**A Theory of Colour on the Basis of Molecular Strain.
Part V. Absorption Spectra and Dissociation
Constants of Organic Salts of Violuric Acid.**

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The present paper is the outcome of an attempt to study the phenomenon of colour in the case of violurates and violuric acid from the point of view of colour put forward by one of the present authors (Dutt, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1926, 129, 1171; *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1927, 4, 99), and thereby to throw more light on the question of the constitution of violuric acid and violurates in solution about which there is a longstanding controversy.

Though much work has been done with the alkali salts of violuric acid (Hartley, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1905, 87, 1797; Hantzsch, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1909, 96, i, 333; Meek and Watson, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1916, 109, 544) from the point of view of colour and chemical constitution, the organic salts of violuric acid mentioned in this paper (most of which are new compounds) have never before been made a study of from the same point of view. These salts of violuric acid are derived from very weak bases, some of which for example have the basicity constants of the order of 10^{-11} , but all the same their solutions have colour which is in no way less intense than that shown by the solutions of alkali violurates. This goes to show that the high basic nature of the base is not very essential to produce the colour phenomenon. It may, as will be shown later on, intensify the colour to some extent. It should also be noted that in the case of alkali violurates, the salt being a combination of strong base and weak acid, we have

where MA denotes the salt of violuric acid with the alkali base M·OH, and HA the violuric acid. Therefore it can be shown that

$$\frac{K_w}{K_a} = \frac{x^2}{(1-x)v}$$

where x = the number of molecules of salt hydrolysed in v litres of water, $K_w = 1.2 \times 10^{-14}$ and K_a = the dissociation constant of the

acid. It will be noted that the amount of hydrolysis is dependent on the dilution and changes from one dilution to another. Consequently in the cases of alkali salts of violuric acid this defect of hydrolysis is present, and for a comparative study of optical properties this cannot be neglected or in any way eliminated. Hence the results of previous workers, who have not taken into account this hydrolysis, cannot be accepted without some caution.

Since the violurates recorded in this paper are derived from weak organic bases, this defect is eliminated. The salts being the products of very weak bases and a weak acid, the amount of hydrolysis is given by

$$\frac{x^2}{(1-x)^2} = \frac{K_w}{K_a \cdot K_b}$$

where x = the number of molecules hydrolysed in v litres of water, $K_w = 1.2 \times 10^{-14}$ and K_a and K_b = the dissociation constants of the acid and base respectively. Since the above expression is free from v , it is apparent that the amount of hydrolysis is independent of the dilution. Moreover the factor K_b being almost the same in most of the cases investigated, the amount of hydrolysis is practically the same in all the cases. Consequently in a comparative study of their optical effect, it is eliminated. Therefore these violurates suited our purpose better than the alkali violurates.

Magnaninni (*Gazzetta*, 1894, **24**, I, 46) has shown that violuric acid has an affinity constant $K = 0.0272$. In aqueous solution containing a gram molecule of the acid in 256 litres, about 8% of the molecules are present dissociated into their ions. Such a solution is colourless or at best has a very light colour, and the ions according to Ostwald and Donnan should be practically colourless. The same author measured the colour of solutions of sodium, potassium and ammonium violurates at various dilutions and came to the conclusion that the absorption is directly proportional to the number of gram molecules of salt present and not to the number of free ions. Furthermore he showed that the addition of potassium nitrate to the solution sufficient to diminish the electrolytic dissociation by 25% has no effect on the absorption. These experiments of Magnaninni leave the conclusions of Ostwald and Donnan very doubtful. Another fact which goes against their hypothesis is that violuric acid and in fact most oximido compounds when heated exhibit abnormally large coefficients of conductivity and also large

dissociation constants, but this phenomenon finds no parallel change in colour (Guinchant, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1899, 76, i, 781; Hantzsch, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1909, 96, i, 331).

These facts clearly point to the fact that the colour phenomenon is not intimately connected with the electrolytic dissociation of violurates, and suggest that the substance in solution must have undergone some fundamental change in constitution so as to produce these interesting optical properties. It has been shown by one of the present authors (Dutt, *loc. cit.*) that a double bond between a nitrogen and an oxygen atom produces the greatest effect on the colour and absorption spectra of organic compounds, and consequently the true nitroso compounds are highly coloured. On account of the great molecular strain existing in all these substances, they are as a matter of fact very unstable and consequently undergo oxidation and reduction with the greatest ease, with formation of nitro- and amino-compounds with comparatively smaller degree of molecular strain. Many of the nitroso compounds tend to lose their internal strain by formation of bimolecular ring compounds :

But if the nitroso group is in a molecule containing a labile hydrogen atom, it automatically rearranges itself to a condition of less strain in the following manner :

A typical example of this nature is isonitroso-malonyl-urea or violuric acid, which is usually represented by the formula (I)

and since this compound is a fairly strong acid of monobasic character, it is probably quite reasonable to assume such a structure for violuric acid with the hydrogen atom marked by asterisk to be replaceable by metals.

This formula is known as the 'oximino-ketonic' formula, and besides this there is also an alternative nitroso-enolic structure (II) which is equally capable of formation.

This latter structure represents violuric acid as containing the highly strained nitroso group, and if such a form be correct then we should expect violuric acid to be a highly coloured substance. While on the other hand, if the oximino-ketonic form be correct, then violuric acid should not have any colour at all, or at best only a pale yellow colour.

Now as a matter of fact we find that violuric acid is almost colourless in the solid state, while in aqueous solution it has a pink colour, the absorption spectra of which has been determined by a number of chemists (Donnan and Schneider, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1895, 95, 956; Morton and Tipping, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1925, 127, 2514) and has been found to have a maxima at about wave-length 5300 λ . From this it is apparent that violuric acid must have a configuration which is tautomeric between (I) and (II) according to the existing circumstances. Thus in the solid state violuric acid should have the comparatively little strained configuration (I), while in solution the more highly strained structure should be present. But on account of the lightness of the hydrogen atom and the consequent ease with which it is transferred from one position to another, this tautomerism between the two forms of violuric acid should be very rapid, and the full colour that is expected of such a structure as (II) would not be developed.

This state of things becomes somewhat modified when an alkali metal salt is taken instead of violuric acid. Under such circumstances on account of the greater load and consequent difficulties of tautomerism from one form to another, the more highly strained nitroso-enolic form will be more stable whenever its existence is possible. The —CO— group in position 6 is really the residue of a carboxyl, and still retains its carboxylic character in a modified form on account of the proximity of the —NH— group, whose basic character it has more than neutralised. Therefore when such a —CO— enolises by the transference of a labile hydrogen atom, it becomes as much acidic in character as a carboxyl, and therefore more so than an —N.OH group. Hence it can be easily seen that in an aqueous solution of violuric acid the latter exists mainly in form (I) with only a small proportion of form (II). But as soon as an alkali like sodium hydroxide is added to the solution, in order to neutralise the highly alkaline character of the latter, the original weakly acidic oximino-ketonic form of violuric acid has to tautomerise to the more acidic nitroso-enolic form. And in this form it becomes fixed by

salt formation with sodium hydroxide. But in this type of tautomerism the original slightly strained molecule becomes more highly strained with the result that its absorption spectra become shifted more towards the red end of the spectrum. Hence from this it can be easily seen that the stronger the basic character of the alkali used, the greater will be the transformation into the nitroso-enolic form, and the intensity of colour will be correspondingly greater. This has been actually proved by the investigations of Hantzsch and his co-workers (*Ber.*, 1909, 42, 1066) who have shown that the greater the basic nature of the alkali or alkaline earth used in the salt formation with violuric acid, the greater is the intensity of the colour of the corresponding salt thus formed.

Apart from the consideration of the constitution of violuric acid it will be clear from the results recorded in this paper, that the greater the basic character of the organic base, the greater in general is the production of colour by salt formation with violuric acid. Though it has not yet been found possible to derive any direct mathematical relationship between the dissociation constants and absorption spectra of the organic salts of violuric acid, it may be said in general that as the dissociation increases, the absorption also increases though to a comparatively small extent.

EXPERIMENTAL.

Most of the organic salts of violuric acid described in this paper were prepared by mixing equimolecular proportions of the acid and the organic base in alcoholic solution and on evaporating at the ordinary temperature, large well-developed crystals were obtained. These were then recrystallised from water or dilute alcohol. All the violurates without exception crystallise in fine long needles with silky lustre. In physical appearance they are either violet, pink or blue with occasional specimens of an orange colour. All of them dissolve in water or organic solvents like alcohol or acetone with various shades of pink colour. The salts do not contain any water of crystallisation and are exceedingly pure, as is confirmed by a number of analytical data given at the end of this paper. Most of them undergo decomposition when heated to about 85°, and the same thing happens when they are exposed to atmospheric conditions for a long time.

The absorption spectra and the dissociation constants were determined by the ordinary methods, taking particular care to secure highly accurate results. The results are summarised in the following table:

Absorption Spectra and Dissociation Constants of Organic Violurates.

(V = Violurate.)

Name of the salt.	Appearance.	Colour in aqueous solution.	Dissociation constant.	Molecular conductivity at N/128 dilution.	Absorption maxima (λ) at N/128 dilution.	Analytical data (theoretical values in brackets).
1. Violuric acid	...	Colourless needles.	·9164	$\cdot 2415 \times 10^3$	5905	—
2. Ammonium V	...	Violet	·9262	$\cdot 1049 \times 10^3$	5682	—
3. Methylamine V	...	"	·9016	$\cdot 7547 \times 10^3$	5782	N = 29·4 (29·7%).
4. Dimethylamine V	...	Violet blue	·9140	$\cdot 8091 \times 10^3$	5793	—
5. Trimethylamine V	...	Blue	·9177	$\cdot 7375 \times 10^3$	5713	N = 25·7 (25·9%).
6. Ethylamine V	...	Scarlet	·9104	$\cdot 7257 \times 10^3$	5697	N = 27·4 (27·7%).
7. Diethylamine V	...	Violet	·8887	$\cdot 7265 \times 10^3$	5689	—
8. n-Propylamine V	...	"	·8878	$\cdot 7295 \times 10^3$	5532	N = 25·7 (25·9%).
9. n-Butylamine V	...	Pink	·8763	$\cdot 7147 \times 10^3$	5582	—

THEORY OF COLOUR

10. Aniline V	... Blue	"	"	'7382	'3498 × 10 ³	5673	N = 23.0 (22.4%).
11. <i>o</i> -Toluidine V	... Pink	"	"	'6380	'3023 × 10 ³	5626	N = 21.0 (21.2%).
12. <i>m</i> -Toluidine V	... Greenish blue	"	"	'5575	'3635 × 10 ³	5678	N = 20.8 (21.2%).
13. <i>p</i> -Toluidine V	... Violet	"	"	'6679	'3878 × 10 ³	5684	—
14. Methylaniline V	... "	"	"	'5321	'3475 × 10 ³	5654	N = 21.1 (21.2%).
15. Ethylaniline V	... "	"	"	'5249	'3692 × 10 ³	5654	—
16. <i>o</i> -Phenylenediamine V	... "	"	Red	'4427	'6089 × 10 ³	5694	N = 25.1 (26.5%).
17. <i>p</i> -Phenylenediamine V	... Pink	"	"	'5396	'3527 × 10 ³	5694	—
18. <i>α</i> -Naphthylamine V	... "	"	Pale pink	'2810	'2921 × 10 ³	5499	—
19. <i>β</i> -Naphthylamine V	... "	"	"	—	'8197 × 10 ³ (N/512)	6322	N = 18.9 (18.7%)
20. Pyridine V	... Orange	"	Pink	'5810	'4471 × 10 ³	5692	N = 23.7 (23.8%)
21. Piperidine V	... Blue	"	Deep pink	'8551	'6970 × 10 ³	5697	—
22. Quinoline V	... Orange	"	Pink	'5746	'3969 × 10 ³	5683	—
23. <i>α</i> -Picoline V	... Pink needles	"	"	'5885	'4020 × 10 ³	5692	N = 22.2 (22.4%)

Absorption Spectra and Dissociation Constants of Organic Violorates (contd.)

(V = Violorate.)

Name of the salt.	Appearance.	Colour in aqueous solution.	Dissociation constant.	Molecular conductivity at N/128 dilution.	Absorption maxima (λ) at N/128 dilution.	Analytical data (theoretical values in brackets.)
24. Nicotine V	.. Blue	Deep pink	'6639	'6152 $\times 10^3$	5695	N = 23.1 (23.5%).
25. Morphine V	... "	" "	'7513	'4920 $\times 10^3$	5691	—
26. Brucine V	... Violet	" "	'7273	'5151 $\times 10^3$	5679	—
27. Strychnine V	... Blue	" "	'7721	'5239 $\times 10^3$	5680	N = 14.0 (14.3%).
28. Cinchonine V	... Pink	" "	'6821	'5002 $\times 10^3$	5557	N = 15.2 (15.6%).
29. Quinine V	... Violet	" "	'6086	'4106 $\times 10^3$	5537	—
30. Cocaine V	... Blue	" "	'7655	'4526 $\times 10^3$	5674	N = 12.1 (12.2%)

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